

An Overview on Nondestructive Spectroscopic Techniques for Lipid and Lipid Oxidation Analysis in Fish and Fish Products

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Abstract: Due to the high content of polyunsaturated fatty acids, fish lipids are readily susceptible to oxidation, which leads to serious food deterioration during storage. However, it remains a major challenging task to develop proper and effective assessment of lipid oxidation because the process is complicated and relies on the type of the oxidation agents, lipid substrate, and the environmental factors. This fact, in association with the limitations of traditional methods, which are normally burdensome, time-consuming, and destructive, highlights the great necessity of developing and spreading the use of convenient, cost-effective, and noninvasive alternative methods, such as spectroscopic techniques. As spectroscopic techniques have provided interesting and promising results in the area of fish quality and safety inspection, the goal of this review is to give an overview of research advances in the application of various spectroscopic techniques, namely infrared (IR) spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, and hyperspectral imaging (HSI), for constituent analysis of fish lipids and for oxidation evaluations. These spectroscopic techniques are described in terms of their basic principles and application advantages. Meanwhile, some perspectives on the current situation and future trends are also presented.

Keywords: fish, lipid, lipid oxidation, spectroscopic techniques

Introduction

Fish products have always been considered to be one of the most significant sources of nutrients for mankind. Over the past several decades, many studies have demonstrated the association between fish consumption and the decreased risk of diseases, such as cardiovascular disease (Stone 1996), ischemic heart disease, and stroke (Zhang and others 1999). Fish are rich sources of long-chain omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), which are acknowledged as the key nutrients attributed to the potential protective effects of fish consumption. However, unsaturated carbon-carbon bonds in fatty acids easily account for lipid oxidation that is the major cause of food deterioration, which makes fish one of the most perishable commodities.

Lipid oxidation in fish involves a complex chain of reactions, which are initiated when a labile hydrogen atom is abstracted from a site on the fatty acyl chain to generate a free lipid radical that reacts rapidly with molecular oxygen to produce peroxy radical (Ladikos and Lougovois 1990). The hydrogen is subsequently abstracted from another hydrocarbon chain of peroxy radical to yield hydroperoxide as the essential product of the primary oxidation

(Pearson and others 1977). Hydroperoxides are easily decomposed into a complex mixture of secondary oxidation products including aldehydes, epoxides, hydroxyl compounds, oligomers, polymers, and ketones (Franke 1984). Products from secondary oxidation mainly result in undesirable sensory and biological effects and give rise to toxic compounds frequently related with rancidity (Sun-Waterhouse and others 2013). Since the acceptability of fresh fish and fish products mostly depends on the extent to which such deterioration has occurred, therefore besides the needs for investigating techniques such as drying (Sun and Byrne 1998; Sun and Woods 1997; Delgado and Sun 2002a, 2002b), refrigeration (Sun 1997a, 1997b; Sun and others 1996; McDonald and Sun 2001; McDonald and others 2001; Kiani and Sun 2011) and edible coating (Xu and others 2001) for possible quality maintenance and shelf-life extension, effective analytical methods to assess the extent of oxidation are urgently required.

Plenty of methodologies for determining fat content, fatty acid composition, and lipid oxidation status have been established and implemented to date. The classical approaches for lipid content quantification are gravimetric methods, which are not only time-consuming, laborious, and tedious, but also require a relatively large number of samples. To determine PUFA composition, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), thin-layer chromatography (TLC), and mass spectrometry (MS) are commonly used as powerful techniques. Nonetheless, such methods generally require considerable sample preparation steps to isolate the lipid fraction prior to analysis (Han and others 2011). Compared

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with lipid content and component detection, implementing efficient methods to evaluate the rate and extent of lipid oxidation remains a challenging task because the process is comparatively complex and relies highly on the type of lipid substrate, the oxidation agents, and the environmental factors (Barriuso and others 2013). Furthermore, type of other ingredients, antioxidants, and pro-oxidants present in the food matrix also play an important role in lipid oxidation processes (Eymard and others 2009). Lipid oxidation in muscle foods can be followed by many conventional methods based on primary and secondary oxidation products. Methods applied to assess primary changes include oxygen uptake, loss of PUFAs, and formation of hydroperoxides (peroxide value [PV]). Among these, PV is frequently accepted as a key analyte in lipid oxidation determinations Klaypradit and others 2011. However, it is not always acceptable in industrial applications since PV increases at the initial stage, reaches a peak, and subsequently decreases when exposed to extended oxidation conditions (Satio 1997). Meanwhile, secondary products, such as malondialdehyde (MDA), which is known as secondary oxidation marker, can also be measured. The truth is that methods based on MDA would easily result in either considerable overestimated or underestimated values. Obviously, traditional techniques have some unavoidable limitations, which render them unsuitable for rapid and online analyses.

In order to surmount the aforementioned disadvantages, various novel methodologies have been proposed as alternatives in the analysis of valuable parameters related to fish lipids. Due to recent technological progress in photonics and optics, a great variety of rapid, nondestructive, and cost-effective spectroscopic techniques have been successfully established for food quality, safety assessment, and online monitoring. With regard to lipid oxidation analysis, Barriuso and others (2013) overreviewed a large number of analytical methods to assess oxidative status in food, presenting both traditional tools and advanced methodologies developed over the last decades. Meanwhile, Cheng and others (2013) published a review on applications of spectroscopic techniques for fish quality and safety evaluation. In addition, another review summed up the possibility to apply nondestructive optical techniques including infrared (IR) spectroscopy, computer vision, and hyperspectral imaging (HSI) to evaluate and forecast the quality attributes of seafood (He and others 2015). However, no reviews have been offered focusing on nondestructive spectroscopic determinations of lipid components and measurement of oxidative deterioration especially in fish and fish products, although it is an important research area on food quality and safety and extensive studies have been carried out. Therefore, this paper will provide a representative selection of research advances of various spectroscopic techniques: IR spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy, and HSI for lipid content and oxidation determination in fish and the related products. In addition, several viewpoints on the observed trends and suggestions for future research directions will also be discussed.

IR Spectroscopy Fundamentals

IR radiation, extending from 780 nm to 1 mm is part of the electromagnetic spectrum that can be divided into 3 band segments: near-infrared (NIR: 0.78 to 2.5 μm), mid-infrared (MIR: 2.5 to 25 μm), and far-infrared (FIR: 25 to 1000 μm) (Alvarez-Ordóñez and Prieto 2012). The NIR region can be further divided into 2 sections, namely, short-wave near-infrared (SW-NIR) region (780

to 1300 nm), and long-wave (LW-NIR) region (1300 to 2500 nm) (Cen and He 2007). IR spectral regions expressed in micrometers are clearly defined in Figure 1. The principle of IR spectroscopy technique is based on the interaction between electromagnetic radiation and physicochemical materials of foods. Energy absorption in the IR region will generate an absorption or reflectance spectrum. A great amount of information associated with the molecule bonds can therefore be extracted. The FIR has a low energy and is used for rotational spectroscopy. In the MIR region, spectral signatures result from the fundamental stretching, bending, and rotating vibrations of the tested sample molecules (Cozzolino and Murray 2012). The fundamental stretching vibrations occurring in MIR region can be correlated to the presence of specific functional groups, therefore MIR spectroscopy is particularly useful in biological structural analysis. On the other hand, absorptions in NIR correspond to overtones and combinations of the fundamental bands (Bellon-Maurel and McBratney 2011). The fundamental difference between NIR and MIR spectroscopy has resulted in different characteristics as shown in Table 1. Since NIR spectroscopy is the widely used region for quantitative and qualitative analysis of fish and fish products, this review will primarily focus on applications of NIR spectroscopy technique. There are different NIR spectroscopy measurement modes available for different situations, such as reflectance, diffuse reflectance, transmittance, and interactance, among which transmittance and reflectance modes are widely utilized for quality assessment of fish and the related products (He and others 2015).

Applications

Since IR spectroscopy can be used both as a convenient handheld device and as an online instrument for noninvasive analysis of fish fillets on a conveyor belt, it has been developed into a promising method for industrial applications. NIR spectroscopy is available for detecting components with merely 0.1% concentration (Cen and He 2007). Therefore, it has been sparingly utilized in many food areas (Sun 2009). In addition, using NIR spectroscopy to determine chemical compositions of fish products have been reported by various researchers, with the evaluation of fat content being one of the prime targets.

One of the early applications was conducted by Sollid and Solberg (1992) who applied this technique in the wavelength NIR region (700 to 1100 nm) to predict fat concentration in fresh minced salmon fillets. The result ($R^2 = 0.99$) achieved by using transmission mode was quite satisfying. When spectra were recorded through skin and scales by means of a fiber optic probe, comparably good results were reported with standard error of prediction (SEP) of 2.0% and 1.45% for dorsal and ventral lipid, respectively (Downey 1996). By detecting on the position between posterior insertion of the dorsal fin and the anterior insertion of the adipose fin of the whole rainbow trout Lee and others (1992) improved accuracy for NIR spectroscopy prediction of lipid ($R^2_c = 0.81$, SEP = 2.27%) with fiber optic probe in the range from 700 to 1050 nm. More recently, some studies have been carried out to testify that NIR spectroscopy is an accurate and rapid method to quantify fat components in tuna fish, with R^2 being 1.95 and 0.96 for total fat and free fat, respectively (Khodabux and others 2007). In addition, Folkestad and others (2008) presented an agreement by applying NIR spectroscopy to measure fat concentration in salmon muscle and observed the correlation between chemical and NIR analysis ($r = 0.94$). In the view of these studies, prediction of lipid content by IR spectroscopy proves satisfactory in the intact fillet portions, and the accuracy could be further

Figure 1—Infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum.

Table 1—Different characteristics between NIR and MIR spectroscopy

Region name	Wavelengths	Less sample preparation requirements	High sensitivity to physical structure and presence of water	High sensitivity to chemical compositions	Deeper light penetration
NIR	0.78 to 2.5 μ m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
MIR	2.5 to 25 μ m			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

enhanced when the fish fresh is minced and used in the measurement (Xiccato and others 2004).

Meanwhile, IR spectroscopy has also succeeded in providing important information to measure lipid oxidative status in fish and fish products. One of the significant parameters that affect fish quality is free fatty acids (FFA), which are formed by hydrolysis of triglycerides, phospholipids, and lipid oxidation products. Previous attempts on the determination of FFAs in fish oil by NIR spectroscopy were made in tandem with multiple linear regression (MLR) and partial least squares (PLS) regression for calibration (Zhang and Lee 1997). Calibration equations recorded from PLS were superior to that from MLR, with higher correlation coefficients of calibration and prediction (r_c and r_p), as well as lower standard errors of calibration and prediction (SEC and SEP). As reported by Sánchez-Alonso and others (2012), mid-Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) established itself as a useful analytical tool to investigate lipid changes during frozen storage. Based on their experiment (Sánchez-Alonso and others 2012), the intensity of the FFA carboxylic band obtained from spectroscopy was capable of monitoring the development of lipid hydrolysis in hake lipids. A similar study was undertaken by Cozzolino and others (2005) who managed to monitor the hydrolytic and oxidative degradation of lipids in fish oil by correlating NIR measurement with reference data of FFA, anisidine value (AV), and PV. The measurement performed well for FFA, with coefficients of determination in calibration (R^2) and standard errors of cross-validation (SECV) being 1.96 and 0.59, respectively, whereas the results for AV and PV showed poor accuracy.

Raman Spectroscopy Fundamentals

Raman spectroscopy technique is a measuring method based on the scattering of monochromatic light which is generally from a laser. Inelastic scattering is produced from the mutual action of monochromatic light and sample material. The sample first absorbs the photons in the laser light and subsequently reemits scattered light (McCreery 2005). Compared with the original monochromatic frequency, the remitted one is shifted up or down, which is acknowledged as the Raman effect (Colthup and others 1990).

One of the remarkable advantages about Raman spectroscopy is its suitability to noninvasively study solid, liquid, and gaseous samples.

It is generally believed that IR spectroscopy and Raman spectroscopy have provided complementary structural information about molecules, yet they are both on the basis of the discrete vibration transitions taking place in the ground electronic state of molecules (Baeten and others 1998). Raman scattering arises from the polarization induced in the molecule by oscillating the electric field of the incoming light. This induced dipole subsequently radiates scattered light, with or without exchange energy with vibrations in the molecule (McCreery 2005). Conversely, IR absorption results from the change of the intrinsic dipole moment with the molecular vibration (Grasselli and Bulkin 1991). Generally speaking, IR peaks are broad and a peak is frequently affected by an adjacent peak or external parameter, whereas a Raman spectrum often contains a series of isolated bands with little interference (Baeten and others 1998). In addition, another main difference relies on the fact that polar groups (such as C = O and O = H) indicate intensive IR absorption bands, while nonpolar groups (such as C = C) interpret strong Raman scattering bands (Yang and others 2005). In brief, IR spectroscopy and Raman spectroscopy give rise to complementary information on the vibrational motions of molecules, both greatly contributing to the unique spectral “fingerprint.”

As shown in Figure 2, a rapid-acquisition Raman spectroscopy system typically consists of 4 major components: laser excitation source, fiber-optic Raman probe, imaging spectrograph, and charge-coupled device (CCD) detector. First of all, salmon fillet is illuminated with a laser beam of light in a wide spectral region from ultraviolet (UV) to NIR ranges (Vodchits and others 2007). Scattered light is then collected in the fiber optic Raman probe and fed into the imaging spectrograph. Elastic scattered radiation is filtered out and the rest of the collected light is dispersed onto a detector which allows the entire spectrum to be recorded simultaneously. Normally, Raman scattering from a sample is very weak, which makes it difficult to separate Raman scattering from the intense stray light. Different kinds of methods concerning sample preparation, sample illumination, or scattered light detection have been developed to enhance the intensity of the Raman signal.

Figure 2—Schematic of a rapid-acquisition Raman spectroscopy system.

For example, stimulated Raman scattering is introduced to obtain nonlinear Raman spectroscopy by a very strong laser pulse (Plotetz and others 2007). In addition, surface-enhanced resonance Raman spectroscopy (SERRS) and surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS) have also been shown to be effective ways to improve Raman spectrum in some conditions.

Applications

As an emerging noncontact technique, Raman spectroscopy has gained considerable popularity in biochemical and chemical structural analysis (Lu and others 2011). It can provide information on structure, concentration, and interaction of biochemical molecules within intact cells or tissues simultaneously (Marquardt and Wold 2004). For fish and the related products, Raman spectroscopy has been extensively employed over the last few decades.

Previous attempts of using Raman spectroscopy to determine fat content in more than 40 samples of ground muscle tissue from farmed Atlantic salmon were performed (Wold and others 2004). With the use of PLS regression, the researchers (Wold and others 2004) obtained a high accuracy ($R^2 = 0.95$) and low root mean square error of prediction (15.5 g/kg). They further identified that both preprocessing and variable selection were able to enhance the result. Similar work was found to elucidate the potential of applying Raman spectroscopy (785-nm excitation) for quantitative measurements of fat in different fish fillets including cod, Pacific halibut, sea bass, and salmon, with principal component analysis (PCA) being performed in semiquantitative analysis (Marquardt and Wold 2004), and the outcome confirmed that Raman spectroscopy generated by a 785-nm laser line and received by a CCD-camera did contain useful quantitative information on fat content in fish.

In relation to lipid composition and oxidation determination, Baeten and others (1998) investigated oil and fat classification by FT-Raman spectroscopy from a large number of edible oil samples including fish oil. They applied PCA to classify the set of samples based on their level of unsaturation. According to their result, scattering intensities near different Raman shifts (3013, 1663, and 1264 cm^{-1}) were highly correlated with the amount of fatty acids assessed by gas chromatography (GC). Interestingly, Afseth and others (2005) managed to determine fatty acid composition in a complex food model system composed of 70 various mixtures of water, protein, and oil blends to establish a rough chemical imi-

tation of fish and meat samples. In addition to that, Raman spectroscopy has been utilized to differentiate the degrees of fatty acid unsaturation (iodine value) of salmon (Afseth and others 2006). In that study (Afseth and others 2006), different spots from the whole salmon muscle, ground salmon samples, as well as oil extracts were detected. Calibration was performed by partial least squares regression (PLSR), and it was found that spectra from oil extracts gave rise to better iodine value prediction than other data sets. The achieved PLSR models with the advantages of simplicity, accuracy, and robustness suggest that Raman spectroscopy is a promising method for determining the level of unsaturation in salmon samples. Later, Beattie and others (2006) found that bulk unsaturation parameters of fatty acid composition from unextracted adipose tissue could be well predicted with a high accuracy ($R = 0.97$). More recently, some pioneer research has been published to employ Raman spectroscopy for lipid deterioration evaluation. For example, FT-Raman spectroscopy was utilized to monitor lipid changes, which took place when hake fillets were under frozen storage (Sánchez-Alonso and others 2012). In view of their study (Sánchez-Alonso and others 2012), the only observed spectral transitions correlated with lipid oxidation during frozen storage were the changes in the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ stretching region (1658 cm^{-1} band), which were partially due to conjugated dienes development.

NMR Spectroscopy

Fundamentals

NMR spectroscopy is one of the most versatile methods in the study of lipids (Namal Senanayake and Shahidi 2007). It is commonly acknowledged that magnetic properties of atomic nuclei have mainly contributed to the physical foundation of NMR spectroscopy (Günter 1995). The principle behind NMR is that the nuclei of many elemental isotopes have a characteristic spin and all nuclei are electrically charged (Akitt and Mann 2000). When an external magnetic field is applied, 2 spin states exist. The energy difference between these 2 spin states depends on the magnetic field strength and the specific nucleus being studied. Irradiation of the sample with radio frequency energy corresponding exactly to the spin state separation of a specific set of nuclei will cause excitation of those set of nuclei in the lower energy state to the higher energy state. The signal is measured in many ways and processed to generate an NMR spectrum for the nucleus concerned. The truth

is that the nucleus in a molecule is surrounded by the electrons of the chemical bonds. Therefore, the effective field is affected by the chemical environment. As a consequence, the resonance frequency varies and this phenomenon is known as the chemical shift (Friebolin and Becconsall 2004).

Low-field nuclear magnetic resonance (LF-NMR) (sometimes also called time-domain NMR) represents a simplified and cheaper version of a traditional NMR spectrometer and operates in the frequency range of 2 to 25 MHz (Aursand and others 2006). This instrument can provide important information about relaxation and diffusion behavior and is capable for online quality control. Therefore, among NMR spectroscopies, LF-NMR has been widely used for food products analysis. Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is usually considered as an extension of NMR. Compared with NMR, MRI provides additional spatial information on nuclear spins.

Applications

NMR spectroscopy plays an important role in the area of food lipids. Satio (1997) underlined the convenience of the NMR method for estimating the overall extent of oxidative deterioration of fish oils during storage due to its simplicity and to the fact that it requires only a small quantity of specimen (less than 20 mg). This technique can extend its use to noncontact quality assessments of fish including pH, water-holding capacity (WHC), collagen content, and metabolites (Erikson and others 2012). Early work was conducted to assess basic quality parameters in an entire fresh salmon fish by employing ^1H NMR spectroscopy (Jepsen and others 1999). Correlations between NMR data and reference data were evaluated by PLSR, accomplishing optimal prediction with root mean square errors of prediction (RMSEP) = 12 g/kg. A few years later, different from the previous research on the fresh fish, Toussaint and others (2002) worked on the fish samples that were dried before NMR measurements. High accuracy was obtained with a prediction error of only 3 g.kg $^{-1}$ fat content between NMR and Soxhlet method determinations ($R^2 = 0.98$). In a subsequent study, Veliyulin and others (2005) broadened NMR application by relating it to online rapid quality control and analysis. A mobile LF-NMR analyzer was employed to evaluate the fat content in live (or slaughtered) Atlantic salmon. In their study, the total fat content per fish was collected in 20 s, and the calibration of the instrument was rapid (<10 min) and robust. The results highlighted the fact that fat content (range 90 to 182 g.kg $^{-1}$) correlated significantly ($R = 0.92$) with chemical extraction data achieved in the same fish (Veliyulin and others 2005). Mobile NMR spectrometry therefore proved its ability in industrial applications, especially for rapid online analysis. Proton NMR spectroscopy was also employed to study lipids of farmed and wild European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) (Vidal and others 2012). The study showed that NMR spectroscopy was able to provide much detailed information about sea bass lipid composition as well as to identify and quantify omega-1 acyl groups in fish lipids. In addition, simple observation based on the signals of the spectra could enable one to distinguish cultured from wild fish. More recently, pioneer research was carried out to investigate the potential of MRI for fat measurement in flesh and subcutaneous fat in fish cutlets (Collewet and others 2013). High correlations were recorded between MRI and vision measurements ($R^2 = 0.77$ and 0.87 for the ventral and dorsal parts, respectively), which confirmed the potential of MRI for lipid studies in terms of abundant samples.

Some studies have also been carried out to estimate the feasibility of using NMR spectroscopy to determine fatty acids

and lipid oxidation. Previous research was undertaken to evaluate the accuracy of unsaturation measurements by using NMR (Johnson and Shoolery 1962). It was demonstrated that a remarkably good agreement between NMR and Wijs iodine number in all fat studied was achieved, except for tung oil. Besides, a 500-MHz ^1H NMR spectrometer was used to determine the contents of docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) in fish oils (mg/g), the molar proportions of total ω -3 fatty acids to all other non- ω -3 fatty acids, and the molar proportions (mol%) of DHA to all other fatty acids in the fish oil (Igarashi and others 2000). Satisfactory results ($R^2 = 0.994$) were recorded between the ^1H NMR and the GC data for molar proportions of DHA. In addition, fatty acids from intact tissues of Atlantic salmon were investigated by using magic angle spinning (MAS-NMR) spectroscopy (Bankefors and others 2011), and it was demonstrated to be successful to calculate the total omega-3 fatty acid content, and the EPA and DHA contents in the muscle as well as in liver tissues directly from the diffusion-edited MAS-NMR spectra without any need for lipid extraction. Most recently, Wu and others (2014) compared the effects of 4 spectroscopic techniques including visible SW-NIR, LW-NIR, MIR, and NMR spectroscopy on the rapid and noncontact determination of 3 important ω -3 PUFAs, namely, EPA, DHA, and docosapentaenoic acid (DPA) in fish oil. PLSR algorithm was used to construct quantitative models between the spectral data and reference PUFA contents of samples. The best predictions for EPA, DHA, and DPA were all observed by NMR spectroscopy (coefficients of cross-validation (r_{CV}^2) of 0.970, 0.982, and 0.983 and the root mean square error of cross-validation (RMSECV) of 11.48, 4.73, and 0.77 mg/g for the EPA, DHA, and DPA predictions, respectively) (Wu and others 2014). Moreover, Guillén and Ruiz (2004) confirmed the usefulness of ^1H NMR spectroscopy not only in determining proportions of various acyl, but also in evaluating the generation rate of oxidation compounds throughout the oxidation process. Therefore, ^1H NMR technique indicated the possibility of studying lipid oxidative stability of fish samples as well as their oxidation degree (Guillén and Ruiz 2004). The above studies confirm that the application of NMR to analyze lipid, fatty acids content, and oxidation process in fish and fish oil enables the direct and rapid detection without the need of extra sample preparation.

Hyperspectral Imaging Fundamentals

In recent years, HSI was found to be a promising analytical tool for food analysis (Kamruzzaman and others 2011; ElMasry and others 2012; ElMasry and others 2011; Kamruzzaman and others 2012; Barbin and others 2012; ElMasry and others 2011; Wu and others 2012). Due to the combination of imaging or computer vision (Sun and others 2003, 2004; Valous and others 2009; Jackman and others 2008, 2009; Wang and others 2002) and spectroscopic technologies, HSI is able to produce a spatial map of spectral variations, which makes it a versatile tool in many applications. An HSI system acquires images with a significant number of contiguous wavelengths. Visible and very-near-infrared range 380 to 800 nm or 400 to 1000 nm are the most widely used in applications of food analysis (Sun 2010). All materials with different chemical compositions and physical structures would reflect, scatter, absorb, and emit electromagnetic energy in distinctive patterns at specific wavelengths, which can be defined as a spectral signature or spectral fingerprint. Due to the 3-dimensional data set, HSI is well-acknowledged as datacube or hypercube (Kim and others 2002). For instance, the hypercube of a piece of fish obtained is elucidated in Figure 3. The raw hyperspectral image

Figure 3–Schematic diagram of hyperspectral image (hypercube) for a piece of fish meat adapted from Sun (2010).

is comprised of a series of contiguous subimages. Each subimage presents the spectral intensity and spatial distribution of the tested sample at a specific wavelength. Figure 3 also shows the difference in spectral signatures between fat pixel and lean fish meat pixel of the tested sample. In brief, hyperspectral data are inherently high-dimensional containing a large number of spectral bands.

Although high-dimensional data offer access to rich information content, a dilemma is encountered for successful data processing, especially when the technique is intended for real-time and online application (Sun 2010). As a consequence, efficient data processing methods are of paramount importance to unmask the truth hidden behind these hypercubes. The 1st data processing method is reflectance calibration, which is performed to improve the comparability of the image data. A dark image (I_{dark}) and white reference image (I_{white}) are recorded and then used in the following equation to correct the raw hyperspectral images (Zhu and others 2014):

$$I_c = (I - I_{\text{dark}}) / (I_{\text{white}} - I_{\text{dark}}) \quad (1)$$

Besides, image enhancement is also a significant process to improve the quality of an image. Image enhancement can be achieved either by making specified image characteristics more obvious, including edge and contrast enhancement, pseudo-coloring, magnifying, and sharpening, or by reducing the noise, such as spatial filtering, Fourier transform (FT), convolution, and wavelet transforms (WTs). In order to enhance the spectral data extracted from hyperspectral, spectral preprocessing algorithms, such as

derivatives, smoothing, multiplicative scatter correction (MSC), and standard normal variate (SNV), are frequently used.

It is also critical to know the necessary steps used to reach the key information. Figure 4 shows the flowchart that outlines typical steps undertaken in an HSI experiment. The 1st step is to collect HSI in ideal acquisition condition, followed by the calibration stage. Before spectroscopic analysis, the spectra are first extracted from various regions of interest (ROIs), which manifest different quality features of that calibrated image. In order to improve the signal-to-noise ratio, it is necessary to preprocess the extracted spectral data. After that, qualitative analysis or quantitative spectral analysis can be implemented. A number of chemometrics tools, such as PCA and PLSR, can be employed to establish models in this stage. In addition, multivariate analysis can reduce the huge dimensionality problems by selecting a limited number of images at some important wavelengths. Technically speaking, the selection of these optimal wavelengths is able to present the most essential information contained in the data space, but with a reduced size of required data. Finally, cross-validation and/or external validation could be applied to check the adaptability and reliability of the developed models (Feng and Sun 2012). According to Sun (2010), results obtained from these steps should be visualized either by scaling, pseudo-color representation, or surface-mapping. Generally, postprocessing methods are undertaken to further enhance the prediction map. It is a tough task to build a satisfactory calibration model, yet its application becomes easy, precise, and fast once the model has been established.

Figure 4—Flow chart of a series of key steps for hyperspectral imaging processing.

Applications

HSI has proved its great capability in the quality and safety assessment of food products (Sun 2010). In relation to the work of fish quality assessment, HSI has been well applied in a diversity of fish species including salmon (Sone and others 2012; He and others 2014), cod (Sivertsen and others 2012), sea bass (Costa and others 2011), rainbow trout (Dissing and others 2011), and halibut (Zhu and others 2013).

Regarding quantification of fat content in fish and fish products, one early example was accomplished by ElMasry and Wold (2008). In their study, 6 species of fish fillets: catfish, mackerel, Atlantic halibut, herring, cod, and saithe were included to obtain quantitative measurements of fat distribution. PLSR was undertaken to analyze spectral data, followed by converting the pixel spectra to a significant distribution map of fat content. The pixelwise prediction model for fat content had a high correlation value of 0.91 with RMSECV of 2.99%, which elucidated the truth that HSI was well suited for high-speed assessment of quality parameters in fish. According to the distribution maps, fat content in the belly area and rims was higher than that in the middle part, which was helpful for the fish industry to sort fish based on fat content and to also precisely cut the fillets according to certain fat thresholds if desired (ElMasry and Wold 2008). Similar experiments were conducted by Zhu and others (2014) with a pushbroom NIR (899 to 1694 nm) HSI system applied to probe fat distribution in Atlantic salmon. The quantitative relationships between spectral data and the reference data were well identified based on PLSR with $R = 0.93$ and $RMSEP = 1.24$. Chemical images for visualizing fat distribution were subsequently built, which elucidated the potential of this technique to predict constituent distributions in fresh fish.

Besides, HSI has also shown promising results in lipid oxidation assessments in fish. For example, Cheng and others (2015) investigated the suitability of HSI (400 to 1000 nm) to monitor lipid

oxidation in fish fillets during cold storage at 4 °C for 0, 2, 5, and 8 d based on the determination of the thiobarbituric acid (TBA) value. The PLSR calibration model, which was developed in the full spectral region between the data extracted from spectral images and the reference TBA values, showed good prediction performance with high determination coefficients (R^2_p) of 0.8325 and low RMSEP of 0.1172 mg MDA/kg flesh. Two simplified PLSR and MLR calibration models were subsequently established using 10 important wavelengths (444, 475, 553, 577, 590, 623, 710, 795, 847, and 937 nm) selected according to weighted regression coefficients. The optimized MLR model provided better results with R^2_p of 0.8395 and RMSEP of 0.1147 mg MDA/kg flesh, which was then applied to visualize the TBA distribution map in fish fillets. These maps were able to interpret dynamic changes of lipid oxidation as well as freshness loss during cold storage, which confirmed the suitability of applying HSI to measure TBA values for evaluation of lipid oxidation in fish fillets (Cheng and others 2015).

However, it is noticeable that the HSI technique normally requires high costs and has difficulties with high-speed data acquisition and processing. Hence, selecting some optimal wavelengths to build a robust multispectral imaging system turns out to be a good alternative to overcome this major bottleneck. In spite of the satisfactory research mentioned above, applications of the HSI technique for lipid content determinations and oxidative detection in fish are limited compared with other spectroscopic techniques. Consequently, the full potential of HSI in this area should be extensively exploited in the future.

Discussion and Future Trends

Nondestructive spectroscopic techniques including IR spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, NMR spectroscopy, and HSI have shown good performance for lipid and lipid oxidation analysis in fish and fish products as illustrated in Table 2. Their basic

Table 2–Applications of spectroscopic techniques for lipid and lipid oxidation analysis in fish and fish products

Fish species and related product	Technique	Analyte	Method	Performance	Related reference
Fish oil	IR	Free fat acids	PCA PLSR	$R^2 = 0.96$ RMSECV = 0.59	Cozzolino and others 2005
		Peroxide value		$R^2 = 0.6$ RMSECV = 2.2	
		Anisidine value		$R^2 = 0.93$ RMSECV = 5.76	
Sea bass minced fillets	NIRS	Lipid	PLSR	$R^2 = 0.97$	Xiccato and others 2004
Tuna fishes skipjack and yellow fin	NIR	Total fat	PLSR	$R^2 = 0.95$	Khodabux and others 2007
Farmed Atlantic salmon (<i>Salmo salar</i> L.)	NIR	Free fat Fat	PLSR	$R^2 = 0.96$ $R = 0.94$, RMSEP = 1.0%	Folkestad and others 2008
Atlantic salmon (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	NIR	Fat	PLSR	$R^2 = 0.99$,	Sollid and Solberg 1992
Rainbow trout (<i>Oncorhynchus mykiss</i>)	NIR	Fat	PLSR	PLS: $R = 0.81$, SEPCV = 2.27%; MLR: $R = 0.76$, SEPCV = 2.48%	Lee and others 1992
Salmo salar	Raman spectroscopy	Fat acid unsaturation	PLSR	$R = 0.87$, RMSEC = 2.5 g I ₂ /100 g fat	Afseth and others 2006
Atlantic salmon	Raman spectroscopy	Fat	PLSR	$R^2 = 0.95$, RMSEP = 15.5	Wold and others 2004
Complex food model system	Raman spectroscopy	Fatty acid composition	PLSR	$R = 0.887$, RMSECV = 2.5	Afseth and others 2005
Fish oil	NMR spectroscopy	ω -3 Polyunsaturated fatty acids	PLSR	EPA: $r^2_{CV} = 0.970$, RMSECV = 11.48 mg/g DHA: $r^2_{CV} = 0.982$, RMSECV = 4.73 mg/g DPA: $r^2_{CV} = 0.983$, RMSECV = 0.77 mg/g	Wu and others 2014
Atlantic salmon (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	NMR spectroscopy	Fat content	–	$R = 0.92$	Veliyulin and others 2005
Rainbow trout cutlets	MRI	Fat content	–	Ventral part: $R^2 = 0.77$ Dorsal part: $R^2 = 0.81$	Collewet and others 2013
Brown trout (Dried)	NMR spectroscopy	Fat content	–	$R^2 = 0.98$	Toussaint and others 2002
Atlantic halibut, catfish, cod, mackerel, herring, and saithe	NIR spectral imaging	Fat content distribution	PLSR	$R = 0.91$, RMSEC = 2.70, RMSECV = 2.99	EIMasry and Wold 2008
Salmon (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	Hyperspectral imaging	Fat content	PLSR	Raw fillets: $R = 0.947$, RMSECV = 1.96% Salted fillets: $R = 0.966$, RMSECV = 1.95%	Segtnan and others 2009
Atlantic salmon	Hyperspectral imaging	Fat content	PLSR	$R = 0.93$, RMSEP = 1.24	Zhu and others 2014
Grass carp	Hyperspectral imaging	Malonaldehyde	PLSR	$R^2_C = 0.8767$ $R^2_P = 0.8325$ RMSEC = 0.1005 mg MDA/kg flesh RMSEP = 0.1172 mg MDA/kg flesh	Cheng and others 2015

Notes: R, correlation coefficient; r^2 , coefficient of determination; RMSEC, root mean square errors in calibration; RMSEP, root mean square errors in prediction; RMSECV, root mean square error of cross-validation; r^2_{CV} , coefficient of determination for cross-validation; PLSR, partial least squares regression; PCA, principal component analysis; MLR, multilinear regression.

Table 3–Characteristics of spectroscopic techniques in food analysis.

Characteristics	IR	Raman	NMR	HSI
Spatial information			☑	☑
Spectral information	☑	☑		☑
Multicomponent information	☑	☑	low	☑
Sensitivity to minor components		☑		☑
Suitable for use at-, on- and in-line process	☑	Problem unsolved (Févote 2007)		☑

principles are compared in Figure 5 in terms of their radiation types, information achievable, and their radiation effects. Due to unavoidable weaknesses of traditional methods, spectroscopic techniques have been proposed as good alternatives for the analysis of lipid content, lipid components, and oxidative status, which makes it possible for applying them in routine procedures as used in the fish industry. Generally, these techniques require

minimal sample preliminary treatments and low sample amount, but provide highly specific results, which earn them merits of being labor-replacing, time-saving, and extremely efficient. In particular, these innovative methods are able to provide real-time and online detection, save much time for workers, and thus produce higher social benefits. Moreover, these measurements are all chemical-free and environmental-friendly, producing no

Figure 5—Principles of different spectroscopic techniques related to wavelength (nanometers) ranges.

environmental pollution during the process of detection. Table 3 lists their major analytical characteristics.

However, there are some intrinsic disadvantages in these spectroscopic methodologies limiting their application in the fish industry. With respect to IR spectroscopy, the difficulty is to build a reliable and robust calibration model, because it usually takes a long time and needs deep knowledge of chemometrics. In addition, each model is used in the limitation of time and spatial variation, even though some methods for model transfer have been suggested (Cen and He 2007). Another major defect arises from the standard or reference method applied for calibration, which, in some circumstances, might result in an accumulated error occurrence. In spite of low measuring cost, the price for an IR spectroscopy instrument is rather high. Hence, future work should focus on developing some simple and low-cost instruments or resolving problems occurred during model transfer from one system to another. Concerning Raman spectroscopy, it should be stressed that some impediments such as radically weak effect of Raman scattering, high instrumental costs, strong interfering of biological fluorescence background signals, and some heat produced by the laser are likely to affect the effectiveness of assessments (Afseth and others 2005). Meanwhile, it is not suitable for materials that emit strong fluorescence, and photolabile compounds generally encounter photodecomposition and photoisomerization attributed to the strong visible laser illumination (Ozaki and others 1992). When it comes to NMR spectroscopy, high cost is normally considered as one of the most serious drawbacks. Besides,

this methodology requires special skills to interpret the spectra and lengthy time for image acquisition (Barriuso and others 2013). Another primary limitation of NMR spectroscopy is the lack of sensitivity (Malet-Martino and Martino 1991). The minimum concentration that can be detected depends upon many factors such as data collection time, field strength, and sample size. Regarding HSI, it provides too much unnecessary information when compared to single-color imaging and thus efforts and specific skills are required to extract desired information from the whole spectral imaging. It is also of great difficulty to accelerate detection speed, eliminate data redundancy, and select optimal wavelengths. Moreover, fish products have strong absorption of light, making them opaque over a distance of about several millimeters in visible and NIR region. Wu and Sun (2013) reported the maximum penetration depth of 13 mm into fish tissue. Therefore, HSI cannot acquire the information of constituents deep inside the fish sample. Without any further extended research, these problems will hinder future applications of HSI in the fish industry. Future research, therefore, should be explored to develop and improve novel algorithms for eliminating data redundancy, progress, and enhance hardware speed of this system and motivate development of a multispectral imaging system that only uses several important wavelengths.

Although a number of researchers have pointed out that applications of spectroscopic techniques have demonstrated great promise in rapid and noninvasive online fish lipid content measurements and lipid composition determinations, there are

in fact not too many publications reporting on lipid oxidation status evaluation in fish and related products by utilizing these state-of-the-art spectroscopic techniques. In particular, researchers involved in such studies normally only focus on a few varieties of fish. The main difficulty may be due to the fact that oxidation process is generally complex containing too many compounds, each of which is indicative of a particular state of oxidation. Correspondingly, it is not simple and reasonable to select just one parameter to inspect oxidative status. Considering the extent of oxidation in a particular food substrate, the decision should be made to determine whether primary or secondary compounds or even both are to be assessed. Hence, attention should be paid to choose appropriate analytes when applying these spectroscopic techniques in the future. In addition, more research should be employed on different kinds of fish to improve and extend the area of applications.

Conclusions

In this review, 4 spectroscopic techniques including IR spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy, NMR spectroscopy, and HSI are summarized as tools to identify lipid components and monitor lipid oxidative deterioration in fish and fish products. IR spectroscopy has shown great ability to provide accurate information regarding fat content and fatty acid composition in intact fish filets. Work has also been done to assess lipid oxidative status in fish oil by analyzing PV and AV, but not too much effort has been recognized in the fresh fish so far. On the other hand, Raman spectroscopy has mainly been applied for analyzing pure oils and fats, but it also has successfully been used to predict fat content, discriminate the degree of fatty acid unsaturation, and evaluate lipid oxidation in fish, among which moderate to good results have been reported. The use of NMR spectroscopy, confirmed by several research groups, has seen very satisfactory for measuring concentrations of FFAs as well as for providing information on the oxidative status. As for HSI, it has been shown to be an emerging technique that provides a valuable tool for fish fat content analysis. However, studies in utilizing HSI for fish lipid oxidation assessments are scarce. Although the newly innovated noncontact spectroscopic techniques are still under development, it is expected that they will soon be used for online and real-time assessments of lipid content and oxidation processes in fish and fish products.

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